

Research

Labor Rights Violation in Ship Recycling Industry: A critical review of International Labor Organization (ILO) Guidelines

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Abstract: *This article provides a brief overview of concerns related to the polluted and dangerous ship recycling industry. Particularly main serious concerns are about the worker's health and safety and the exercise of basic labor rights. The study found that labors are generally not privileged to be similar in ship recycling industry. Paper has disclosed that there is no overtime or paid holidays, ship breakers work long hours and there is usually no contract arrangement with yard management. When fire, disasters and explosions, fall from a height or are hit by large steel/iron blocks. During work, Workers are losing their lives and getting injures Labor rights do not exist; there are no unions and no collective bargaining to raise voice against the violations. The working and living conditions reflect a complete lack of standards. The International Labor Organization has developed guidelines to mitigate risks, problems and problems associated with shipwreck. Labor sought to find sustainable solutions for the swatch and safe disposal of ships.*

Keywords: *International Labor organization Guideline, Dangerous ship-recycling industry, Sustainable solutions, Healthy & safety.*

Introduction

The European Commission's report states that, "Those working at demolition site in Bangladesh, India and Pakistan earn only one or two dollars a day and the cost of hiring for safety and health is negligible. In the Netherlands, it can be estimated at approximately \$250 per day for a worker

in the Netherlands and \$13 USD in Bulgaria.¹ Ship recycling, ship-breaking, scrapping and dismantling is used as synonyms. However, these terms are used by various organizations to describe the final process by which a ship is dismantled or dismantled at the end of its operating life. The term recycling is commonly used on academic ships. Therefore, the term "ship is cycling" is the preferred term used in studies. Generally, the economic age of a commercial global fleet is an average of 25 to 30 years. But sometimes it is not economically viable for owners to operate and sell a ship. 700-800 ships annually exceed 499 GT of the 103,392 coastal vessels around the world.² At the end of the voyage, these vessels are sold and about 95% of the ship's most valuable steel is exported.³ Nearly every part of the ship other apparatus, tools and equipment have been restored to be used in the shipping industry as well as equipment used in other industries or for processing as scrap metal. This process is done either on dry dock, on slippery roads, along walks or on beach sites. The shipbuilding industry is a very laborious business, with hundreds of thousands of people employed. Economic labor costs and poor compliance with safety and labor standards, poor law enforcement systems are an added benefit for businesses. Due to the uncontrolled unemployment prevailing in India, Bangladesh and Pakistan are looking for work regardless of the associated job risks. In each country of the Indian subcontinent, the workforce varies by quantity, but there is an estimated range between 8,000 and 22,000 directly with 200,000 in the supply chain. Shops and re-rolling mills estimated to reach more than 500,000 in Bangladesh alone and less in Pakistan. In India, Bangladesh and Pakistan, swallowing activities are carried out at beach locations using the coastal zone in an uncontrolled environment. It is estimated that up to 95% of the workforce is made up of migrant workers from the poor regions of each country.⁴ Labors are considered main pillar of the industry which is highly ignored by the authorities. The main objective of article is to examine the existing international labor organization guidelines and way to find violation of labor ship-recycling industry.

¹Frey, R. Scott. "Breaking ships in the world-system: An analysis of two ship breaking capitals, Alang India and Chittagong, Bangladesh." (2013).

²Sarraf, Maria, et al. "The ship breaking and recycling industry in Bangladesh and Pakistan." (2010).

³Hossain, Maruf Md M., and Mohammad Mahmudul Islam. *Ship breaking activities and its impact on the coastal zone of Chittagong, Bangladesh: Towards sustainable management*. Chittagong, Bangladesh: Advocacy & Publication Unit, Young Power in Social Action (YPSA), 2006.

⁴<https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/health-environment/article/2170256/two-years-pakistans-gadani-ship-breaking-disaster-why>

Historical Labor Background in Ship recycling industry:

Ships are broken manually from start to finish, with plenty of manual work in the ship recycling industry. The shipping recycling industry employs a large number of people directly, creating regional and regional economic growth. Despite the actual breakers, the dismantling of the ship creates a great deal of additional indirect employment, but there is a separate distribution line for all vessels that have the ship. Labor costs were a major factor in the revolution experienced in the field of ship recycling in the late 20th century.⁵ Like most statistics of ship breakage in South Asian countries, industry employment figures are much less projected because labor is unorganized and the industry is very sensitive to economic fluctuations. By controlling the overall economic cycle, they also cause temporary changes among the ship owners who want to recycle the ship. This is a result of the different needs of scrap ships in developing countries. For example, South Asian countries have become the market leaders for eliminating large tankers because workers can enter ships before conducting proper inspections to ensure they are free of flames before cutting.⁶ The status of workers is low due to the cyclical nature of the industry and the lack of Western labor laws. The need for workers is constantly changing and leads to national migration to developing countries. The instability and danger of the industry has led to a situation in which the work comes from poor regions of the dismantling countries.⁷

Threats Related to Environmental Damage, Safety, Health and Labor Rights:

This section examines current scenarios in terms of worker health and safety. It is more important to discuss your health and working conditions. Shipyards employ, directly or indirectly, thousands of poor migrants.⁸ These immigrants return in shipwrecks and poor living conditions, despite the dangerous and dirty conditions of shipyards. The physical danger is very high and is directly related to the ship recycling yard. Every time about 20% of workers are

⁵Goldstone, Jack A. *Revolution and Rebellion in the Early Modern World: Population Change and State Breakdown in England, France, Turkey, and China, 1600-1850*. Routledge, 2016.

⁶Legaspi, Rolando D. "Ship recycling: analysis of the shipbreaking countries in Asia." (2000).

⁷Vuori, Juho. "Environmental impacts of ship dismantling: screening for sustainable ways." (2013).

⁸Karim, M. (2009). Violation of labour rights in the ship-breaking yards of Bangladesh: legal norms and reality. *International Journal of Comparative Labour Law and Industrial Relations*, 25(4), 379-394.

employed on the ship.⁹The main causes of accidents happening during the breakdown of ships are fires and chemical explosions. ; However, ships are never cleaned before being cut. None of the workers wore climbing equipment in the yards. Protective equipment is not provided to patio workers, but treatment and enforcement are not sound. Other causes of major accidents are people who are stranded due to falling materials and oil leakage. A possible explanation for this discrepancy could be that seriously injured workers were not treated in local hospitals but in well-equipped hospitals. Often, workers get stranded and fall to death from falling objects.¹⁰The general direction of the factory advisory service reports that goods are not properly assembled at construction sites.¹¹ The cutting plan is improper; there was a big fire when a ship was cut and six workers died on August 4 2009, in India.¹² The workers have appealed for a judicial inquiry and have written to the Gujarat Supreme Court Justice. A preliminary report by the GMB concluded that the fire was caused by negligence of the shipyards, at yards there is no any emergency facility to safe burnt labor on time.¹³ Article 23 of the ILO states that: everyone who works and has the right to a fair and reasonable remuneration that ensures a decent life for him and his family and that, combined with other means of social security, is necessary. The ILO has reported that Bangladesh and India have an unacceptably high mortality rate which makes them one of the world's most dangerous jobs.¹⁴

On average 95 percent of the ship's steel is painted with 10 to 100 tons of paint including lead, mercury, zinc, arsenic, chromium, and so on.¹⁵If the ship's processing takes place in the coastal tidal region, the water will wash away contaminants during the tide.¹⁶Ship recycling operations have an impact on the local environment with the release of poisonous emissions into the air and the lack of storage of dangerous materials. Coastal emissions, air pollution, aquatic and groundwater also impact local populations, which can be harmful to farming and

⁹ Andersen, Aage Bjørn. "Worker safety in the ship-breaking industries." *International Labour Office, Geneva* (2001).

¹⁰Chang, Y. C., Wang, N., &Durak, O S. (2010).Ship recycling and marine pollution. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 60(9), 1390-1396.

¹¹ Model Ship Breaking Yard- A study report, Roy Choudhari, Directorate General Factory Advice Service, Central Labour Institute, Sion Mumbai, 2001

¹²<http://archive.indianexpress.com/news/along-fire-incident-workers-union-demands-judicial-probe/500466/>

¹³ Preliminary report on fire by GMB under the chairmanship of Capt. S.C. Mathur

¹⁴International Labour Organisation, 'Shipbreaking:

AHazardousWork',http://www.ilo.org/safework/info/WCMS_110335/lang--en/index.htm, February 201

¹⁵M. I. Talukder et al., 'Environmental Impacts of Ship Breaking and Recycling Industry of Sitakunda, Chittagong, Bangladesh',

Advances in Natural Science 8:1 (2015) 51 -58 at 53

¹⁶ NGO Shipbreaking Platform, Annual Report 2014 (NGO Shipbreaking Platform, 2015) at page #3

fishing.¹⁷ Ship recycling was described by the International Labor Organization (ILO) in 2004 as one of the most dangerous occupations in which employees are at high risk of death and injury.¹⁸ Safety and safe disposal of ships are listed in the ILO Guidelines specifically for Asian countries and the most common causes of injury or death accidents in Turkey, including: hazardous substances and waste, as well as physical, mechanical, biological, ergonomic and psychosocial hazards.¹⁹ More recent reports confirm that fatal and serious accidents are still frequent, particularly in developing countries, during ship-recycling.²⁰ Long-term hazardous waste exposure results in both injuries and illnesses. The regulation of working conditions does not follow the international requirements is also discussed. Staffs lost their lives and were wounded when explosions of oil tanks and steel plates fell during work on the labs. Some die because of a shortage of safety gear. Many vessels for finishing include flammable liquids, gases, and materials. Additionally, some accidents occur due to failure to comply with the precautions needed before the fire is cut during the digressing process. The obtainable Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) is minimal, and burning injuries are common.²¹

There are long-term health-related hazards associated with the ship's breakage. A research carried out in 2015 found higher concentrations of PCB, PAH and HCB in the air near ship scrapping areas than in Chittagong. Inhalation of these substances raises human health risks.²² For instance, PCBs are known as human cancers, meaning that they are directly involved in cancer.²³ As Taiwanese ship yards have a higher cancer risk compared with the general population, likely due to asbestos exposure.²⁴

¹⁷Summary of Annual Reports 1996-2014 (UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, 2015) at 18.

¹⁸International Labour Office, Safety and Health in Shipbreaking: Guidelines for Asian countries and Turkey (International Labour Organization, 2004) at p. 4

¹⁹International Labour Office, Safety and Health in Shipbreaking: Guidelines for Asian countries and Turkey (International Labour Organization, 2004) at p. 8.

²⁰ NGO Shipbreaking Platform, Annual Report 2014 (NGO Shipbreaking Platform, 2015) at p:3

²¹NGO Shipbreaking Platform, Why Ships are Toxic (NGO Shipbreaking Platform, 2012) at 2

²²T. H. Nøstet al., 'High Concentrations of Organic Contaminants in Air from Ship Breaking Activities in Chittagong,

²³International Agency for Research on, List of Classifications, volumes 1-114 (World Health Organization, 2016) Retrieved 20 January 2016 from <http://monographs.iarc.fr/ENG/Classification/latest_classif.php>

²⁴W.-T. Wu et al., 'Asbestos is main cause of cancer to labors in Shipbreaking Workers: A Matched-Cohort Study', PloS ONE 10:7(2015) 1 -12. A 2014 study had similar findings, see W.-T. Wu et al., 'Cancer Incidence of Taiwanese Shipbreaking Workers who have been victim/affected to Asbestos', Environmental Research mentioned 132 (2014) 370-378. Shipbreaking in Taiwan took place in the Kaohsiung deep water port using a method similar to pier breaking. However, the working conditions resemble that of South Asian yards, as the called graveyard which was carried out using cutting torches and limited PPE, and with a significant number of

Condition of Labors under ILO guidelines

In 2004, ILO Health adopted a set of guidelines covering occupational health and safety aspects of shipwreck. The guidelines are designed to assist ship recycling and competent authorities to improve implementation for ILO standards, occupational health and safety working conditions, and other relevant international organizations.

The practical recommendations of these directives are intended for all those responsible for occupational safety and health in ship recycling operations. As it is noted that ILO directives are not legally binding and are not intended to replace accepted national laws, regulations or standards, they provide guidance to those involved in the development of relevant provisions and the establishment of effective national systems and corporate regulations. Where there is no special orientation.

Challenges and Limits of the ILO's Ship Recycling Guidelines in South Asia:

There are many dangerous to the lives of the laborers coming to the demolition. Resident and migrant laborers are suffering from chemicals in ships. The biter, who is set up by the Supreme Court of India to revoke the permit, but the reality is complicated, which is not practicable. The International Regulatory Framework for Ship Recycling is developing the International Maritime Organization and the International Labor Organization (ILO). The main purpose is to promote cooperation between the parties in the international trade of certain hazardous chemicals to protect human health and the environment. At the Rotterdam meeting on September 10, 1998, the principle of "informed consent in advance" was adopted as a common responsibility. The convention creates legally binding obligations to carry out procedures.²⁵ The discussion at the United Nations has lasted seven years, but no conclusion has yet been reached. The ILO cannot impose directives in South Asian countries. The guidelines are intended to help local

casualties. For detailed: M.Stopford, *Maritime Economics* 2nd ed. (London: Routledge, 1997) at 486; Reuter, *Taiwan Ship-Scrapping Firms are Heading for the Scrap Heap* (Reuter, 1988)

²⁵Engels, Urs Daniel. *European Ship Recycling Regulation: Entry-Into-Force Implications of the Hong Kong Convention*. Vol. 24. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.

authorities establish the respective duties and responsibilities of authorities, employers and workers and to enable them to cooperate. In addition to this, a number of other conventions and treaties under the ILO flag are important to ship-dumping countries.

- Clause 87, Freedom of Association and Protection of the Right to Organize Convention, 1948 (ratified by India and Bangladesh)
- Clause 98, Rights to Organize and Collective Bargaining Convention, 1949 (ratified by India and Bangladesh)
- Clause 1, Hours of Work (Industry), 1919 (ratified by India and Bangladesh)
- Clause 18, Workman's Compensation Conventions, 1925 and 1934 (ratified by India and Bangladesh) context

The International Labor Organization focuses on training workers to fully understand and avoid hazards. The current status of occupational health and safety training in ship recycling industry,²⁶ South Asian countries do not have strength and does not comply with minimum requirements. In fact, low levels of awareness of short-term seasonal workers may be associated with risks or limited training, jeopardize the health, safety, and environment protection.²⁷ In its 2009 Verdict 6/4/11 the Bangladesh High Court concluded that adequate training should be provided to workers in ship recycling yards, which led the Bangladesh Ship Scrapping Association (BSBA) to build a training center.²⁸

A Critical Review of ILO Guidelines

The main goal of decision makers is to reduce death, injury and health risks in ship recycling industry. There are important ways to improve worker conditions for the sustainability of the South Asian ship recycling industry.²⁹ Health and environmental safety should be the main goals for safety and healthy environment. Currently, the labors are not trained well and mostly they are

²⁶Rahman, S. M., et al. "Uncovering discursive framings of the Bangladesh ship breaking industry." *Social Sciences* 7.1 (2018): 14.

²⁷Devault, Damien A., BriacBeilvert, and Peter Winterton. "Ship breaking or scuttling? A review of environmental, economic and forensic issues for decision support." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 24.33 (2017): 25741-25774.

²⁸Gunbeyaz, Sefer A., Rafet E. Kurt, and Raphael Baumler. "A study on evaluating the status of current occupational training in the ship recycling industry in Bangladesh." *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs* 18.1 (2019): 41-59.

²⁹Devault, Damien A., BriacBeilvert, and Peter Winterton. "Ship breaking or scuttling? A review of environmental, economic and forensic issues for decision support." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 24.33 (2017): 25741-25774.

uneducated. Need to take into account socio-economic conditions for the workforce, as well as supply their opportunity costs and flexibility. In 2004, the International Labor Organization developed guidelines entitled "Safety and Health in Ship Disposal for Asia and Turkey" and the ILO proposed the implementation of these guidelines in countries where ship breaking downs have become a promising industry. The maintenance of health and safety at work (OSH)³⁰ is the main objective of these ILO guidelines. All Asian countries have followed the rules and standards of OSH since the beginning of their activities, in industries are associated with huge professional risks and health hazards. Some specific guidelines are still required to protect workers in this industry. After reviewing the ILO guidelines, this important guideline is missing from the whole guideline, making it a worthless as a political tool and avoiding the basic rights of labor.

1. The registration and introduction system for labor is a missing issue in 'Ship Breaking Safety and Health: Instructions for Asian Countries and Turkey - 2004.'³¹
2. There is no significant clause regarding the policy of hiring workers. It is studied that in ship recycling an approved contractor hires a daily laborer in search of a daily and unskilled and manual job without keeping a record of the worker's identity, even if there is no register / work name and Attendance register to write the identity. The weekly documentation related to the works is a justification in the ship recycling yard. And no domestic government is still concerned about this issue and the ILO has done so without imposing any restrictions in its directive.³²

Critical review of ILO Guidelines structure

The clause 3.8.2 (b) states that contractors must be registered or licensed, but there is no provision for registering new employees by profession. Because of this gap, contractors do not report work-related injuries or deaths, nor do they pay minimum compensation to victims. The companies involved in importing and destroying ships have the same owners with different trade names and licenses. While ship importing companies and ship breaking contractors are

³⁰Niu, Shengli. "Ergonomics and occupational safety and health: An ILO perspective." *Applied ergonomics* 41.6 (2010): 744-753.

³¹Karim, Md. "Violation of labour rights in the ship-breaking yards of Bangladesh: legal norms and reality." *Int'l J. Comp. Lab. L. & Indus. Rel.* 25 (2009): 379.

³²Hossain, Maruf Md M., and Mohammad Mahmudul Islam. *Ship breaking activities and its impact on the coastal zone of Chittagong, Bangladesh: Towards sustainable management*. Chittagong, Bangladesh: Advocacy & Publication Unit, Young Power in Social Action (YPSA), 2006.

sometimes different from each other, they also prioritize their trading relationships and disregard most of the rules required in the guidelines, entering into negotiations to get rid of them and there is must be fine or compensation for accidents and support business reputations of labors.

The clause 4.3.1(e) states that before starting work, an employer or contractor should analyze previous data to ensure work safety and health. Most of the world's ships are broken by hand on the beaches of South Asia.³³ When hiring labor, the contractor avoids registering his name and does not sign any agreement. The contractor hires them on a daily basis, so employers or contractors have never done an analysis of the data, since most workers have no record with their employers or contractors.

The clauses 4.3.2 and 4.4.1 emphasize the first review and analysis of data to develop a systematic process for safety measures and health and safety policies in the ship recycling industry. The basic reality differs from the previous clauses. Around 50 workers die each year. Injuries and burning are very common. In a critical scenario, it is clear that safety measures are not taken for workers working in the shipyard. Most of the work is illiterate and not trained. They have no knowledge or recommendations about their work. As a result, more accidents occur, leading to serious injuries and deaths. The main random cause is the explosion of residual gas and steam in the tank. Falling from a high altitude is also a major accident. Workers intend to cut the shell on the front. This practice causes the slab to come down from a higher position.

Section 4.4.1 is a guide to risk mitigation prevention and safety, which is a fixed cost for ship-importing firms and ship-breaking contractors. Since shipping and importing companies in Bangladesh are small capitalists and the majority of their capital comes from bank loans, they incur high fixed costs to implement the necessary measures to mitigate risks. They therefore want to offer a larger amount of relief than embracing prevention and safety. These fixed costs are more than the total compensation cost, which does not have to be paid for each accident. If the International Funding Agency or the shipping-exporting company supports them to cover a portion of these fixed costs, this policy guideline will probably be implemented.

³³Lloyd's Register (2011) *Ship Recycling: Practice and Regulation Today* [Online]. Retrieved on 17 August 2013 from:
[http://www.shipbreakingbd.info/report/ShipRecycling_Lloyds% 20Register.pdf](http://www.shipbreakingbd.info/report/ShipRecycling_Lloyds%20Register.pdf)

The protective measures mentioned in Section 4.4.3 (d) could be implemented if those workers were registered with the leasing company or shipping importer. Lack of security equipment, safety suits and ventilation can cause serious accidents when working in confined spaces. Inappropriate gas frying from cargo vessels and cutting of panels from gas monitoring processes creates serious fire hazards, which pose a risk to workers. Minor accidents are very common, such as brushing, broken bones when carrying heavy metals, cutting through sharp edges are always done now and then in a ship-breaking yard. Lack of first aid, emergency departure, emergency response and rescue is also common in the shipwreck industry in South Asian countries. Worker dies while working in a ship-breaking yard, the family does not get much relief from the ship-breaking yard. The worker does not get the right compensation. The family is living worse after an injury and death.

Conclusion

To work in the worldwide shipping recycling industry and to enforce international law there must be permanent legal protection. There is the need to improve workers' health and safety and environmental conditions in shipping recycling countries in the South Asia. The ILO labeled ship recycling as one of the most dangerous jobs in the world. The ILO has named ship recycling the world's most dangerous occupation.³⁴ Action is urgently needed to prevent workers' injury and fatal incidents and to minimize the negative effects of this activity on the environment. There are a number of solutions to the problems that arise in a shipwreck yard: it is open to question whether any of them will work. The industry is tireless in handling these risky practices and can only change if the attitudes of the people in charge change with it. South Asian countries must work to improve the situation, From time to time, domestic governments, recyclers and ship owners have resorted to a hollow proposal to transport more than 5 lacks people from the region, depending on scraping. The living acquaintance of new practices is against them rather than in their favor. The change to date is precisely what is desirable here to create an adequate, economical and environmentally sustainable system for workers.

³⁴International Labour Organisation, 'Shipbreaking: A Hazardous Work', http://www.ilo.org/safework/info/WCMS_110335/lang--en/index.htm, February 2017

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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